

THE PROCESS OF DIGITAL CITIZENSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE GEORGIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract

In the era of digital transformation, people have to live in a rapidly changing world, the horizon of which is expanding more and more. Technologies not only allowed them to have new and pleasant experiences but also added a completely new dimension to their daily life, which involves inclusion and participation in the virtual and online spaces. Technology fundamentally changes the nature of education and the skills needed to be an informed citizen, a productive worker, a good teacher, and a parent. Nowadays, teenagers, unlike their parents' generation, are full-fledged heirs to the digital world. Therefore, their digital awareness and skills are clearly and distinctly better than older generations'. Still, at the same time, adults are more aware of the dangers that today's generation of children may face as they enter adulthood. Thus, it is the responsibility of the education system to prepare young people to deal with the challenges they will inevitably face and ensure that the younger generation is ready not only in the physical world but also in the digital world to deal with the challenges that lie ahead of them - the next generation needs to be prepared not only in the real world For life but also for living in the virtual world.

The paper examines the current situation and features of digital citizenship competence in the educational space of Georgia and determines the possibilities of its improvement.

Keywords: Education System, Digital Citizenship, Digital Transformation.

Introduction. In the twenty-first century, the world lives in the information age. Virtual reality makes each of us a digital product creator and consumer simultaneously. Supporting the introduction of modern digital technologies and the digitization process, and therefore establishing a worthy place in the world information space, is considered a priority task of our country. Successfully solving this task is crucial for achieving such strategic goals as the creation of a democratic, free, and legal state, development of civil society, security of the country, protection of human rights, and fight against poverty and corruption, extremism, and terrorism. It is crucially important that the active use of digital technologies in the education system not only provides technical skills to young people but also creates favorable conditions for a free personality carrying national and social values formation.[1]

For today's children, digital technologies are a part of everyday life, and social networks are vital. This circumstance became especially visible in the conditions of the global COVID-19 pandemic. According to 2022 statistics, the Internet has 5.03 billion daily users [2]. The intrusion of technology into the modern world has its pros and cons. According to the non-governmental agency that regulates British television and radio companies, the vast majority of European children start using technology before the age of 2, and children between the ages of 3 and 4 spend an average of 71 minutes online per day. Watching videos posted on YouTube has become the second favorite activity of children under five years of age, while at this age, physical activity and learning through games are vital for a child's physical, mental, and socio-psychological skills development and formation [3]. Similar problems are in Georgia as well social networks are sleepy for the young generation. Therefore, dealing

with the challenges of the digital world and determining the right direction is significant. It's essential for the modern person to have the necessary competencies to act safely and ethically in the digital world, making him a literate digital citizen.

Due to the fact that information technologies and systems were implemented in Georgia much later, the phenomenon of digital citizenship remains a challenge for Georgia. Thus, the paper aims to reveal the existing problems in terms of digital citizenship competence in the field of education within the digital transformation framework in Georgia, evaluate and analyze modern trends, and offer appropriate recommendations for the Georgian educational space.

The research purpose and objectives. The study aims to analyze the features of the development of digital citizenship in the education system in Georgia and determine the possibilities for its improvement.

Research methodology. In the research course, relevant scientific literature and studies were analyzed, and a comparative analysis of the retrieved material and statistical data was carried out. Conclusions and recommendations were developed.

Literature review. Digital reality is the greatest challenge of the modern era. In 2019, the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe approved the recommendation "On Education for Digital Citizenship," a digital citizen is a person who develops skills and knowledge to use the Internet and other digital technologies effectively, especially for responsible participation in social and civic activities. The concept of digital citizenship emphasizes the positive aspect of technology – universal access to navigation in the digital world. [4]

Education for digital citizenship means considering global citizenship in an educational context, where knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes

are formed through education for global citizenship [5]. Digital citizenship education is considered in formal and informal contexts, considering the rights of citizens. The task of formal educational institutions is to develop an appropriate complex education program for digital citizenship and systematically include it in educational programs for its effective implementation. Digital citizenship can be said to be:

- A thoughtful and positive relationship with digital technologies (creating, processing, sharing, socializing, researching, playing, interacting and learning);

- Participant's activity and responsibility (values, attitudes, skills, knowledge) at all levels of society (local, national, global) and in all areas (political, economic, social, cultural and intercultural);

- Continuous formal and informal education process;

- Constant protection of human dignity.

An educational structure built according to these goals is essential for effective learning opportunities development throughout life and at all levels.

Compared to previous years, the education system of Georgia has made significant progress in teaching digital citizenship, which is reflected in the form of relevant changes in education policy documents. In particular, in the updated versions of the 2020 National Curriculum and Teacher's Professional Standard - a note on digital citizenship appeared for the first time. The second chapter of the 2020 edition of the third generation (2018-2024) National Curriculum - "Teaching-Learning Goals and Educational Principles" - mentions the importance of digital and media literacy as components of general literacy in the age of communication and digital technologies. The digital literacy competence development among students is not only determined by the standard of computer technology subject. It is and should become a penetrating competence. The standard includes cyber awareness, digital, media, and information literacies. It is worth noting that the national curriculum reflects not only achievable results but also differentiates between the level of competence and its indicators and offers relevant examples [6].

In addition, the Government of Georgia has approved the "2021-2024 National Cyber Security Strategy of Georgia and its Action Plan", and it is noteworthy that for the first time, it includes an education component, which, in turn, includes general and higher education levels, where teaching digital citizenship - as a multidisciplinary field, includes both cyber awareness and a combination of digital security, media literacy, digital literacy, and other related competencies. The strategy action plan involves its implementation with the involvement of the Ministry of Education and Science and the National Communications Commission. The significant tasks in the strategy are: "Developing the skills and raising the level of education for schoolchildren and students to function safely and securely in cyberspace, raising the awareness of the information society and organizations about cyber threats and risks for functioning safely and securely in cyberspace, and providing training courses

and learning materials to promote digital citizenship." [7]

Discussion/Results. The digital transformation process and the involvement of the education system in it - are significant for our country. The education sector is assigned a leading role in the reform implementation and introduction of innovation processes. Accordingly, more and more attention is paid to the education system's readiness to raise awareness and impart knowledge related to digital citizenship.

According to the "Unified National Strategy of Education and Science of Georgia 2022-2030" approved by Resolution N446 of the Government of Georgia on August 31, 2022, "the pandemic caused by COVID-19 has accelerated the pace of digital transformation. It is expected that the rapid development of digital technologies with the automation of processes will increase the demand for technological, social, emotional, and higher cognitive skills. Demand for physical and basic cognitive skills will decrease. From this point of view, the challenge in the wake of digital transformation is not only the development of skills and competencies but also the strengthening of the ecosystem of digital education and science". [8]

Becoming a digital citizen is a lifelong process. Digital citizenship education aims to create opportunities for all individuals to develop a range of citizenship-related competencies.

The formation of digital citizenship impacts all stakeholders involved in this process, namely family members, the local community, teachers, schools, government, and all those groups that offer citizens online tools and platforms. In this case, for introducing digital literacy practices among children, local educational institutions contribute to the formal and non-formal education systems development. Considers the possibility of introducing the so-called "civic technologies," which implies using technologies to manage the various digital citizenship-related aspects. In addition, in the digital citizenship establishing process, regulatory bodies should protect children's rights and, at the same time, support the authorities' efforts - responsible for education-related issues in the direction of providing citizens with digital education. National leadership should promote the protection of fundamental rights and democratic values through multilateral (multi-stakeholder) governance structures. [9]

Conclusion. Therefore, developing digital citizenship teaching in the education field is significant. Digital transformation does not mean only the emergence of high-tech startups in the market. The main thing is the consistent introduction of intelligent technologies in all sectors, which is possible with the joint efforts of the state, business, and educational sectors. The barriers in this direction primarily include the problems in the education system and the lack of digital consumer awareness, which are the prerogative of the state to solve.

Since digital citizenship is a new field in our country, its legal base is scarce. It is worth noting that so far, there is only the national cyber security strategy

of Georgia for 2021-2024 and its action plan, the significant task of which is to develop the skills necessary for schoolchildren and students to function safely and securely in cyberspace and raise the level of education. In order to achieve the set task, the Ministry of Education and Science function is introducing "digital citizenship" teaching at all three levels of general education schools in Georgia (primary, basic, and secondary). The National Curriculum of General Education (2018-2024) changed according to the Cyber Security Strategy.

Thus, assuredly, the education system bears a great responsibility and plays a remarkable role in the digital citizenship development for the adolescent generation. The education system is responsible for preparing young people for the ever-changing environment of the digital world and raising a conscientious, active, good digital citizen.

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